

CHARACTERISTICS OF PERSONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL PROTECTION IN EXTREME SITUATIONS

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Annotation: The article describes the specific features of psychological protection of a person in extreme situations, analyzed them from a psychological point of view and gave their descriptions. Also, the dynamics of the extreme situation and its uniqueness were fully studied.

Key words: Semantic, stereotypic, regulatory, dominant, stress, distress.

Аннотация: В статье описаны особенности психологической защиты человека в экстремальных ситуациях, проанализированы их с психологической точки зрения и даны их характеристики. Также полностью изучена динамика экстремальной ситуации и ее уникальность.

Ключевые слова: Смысловой, стереотипный, регулятивный, доминантный, стрессовый, бедствие.

An extreme situation is understood as a change in human consciousness and behavior under the influence of extreme factors or extreme mechanisms, as well as the state of their exposure under pressure. It is characterized by a violation of adaptation to physiological effects (such a situation often arises under the influence of extreme factors of a physical or chemical nature) or a violation of psychological and moral influence (it is more often under the influence of extreme factors of an informational-semantic nature characteristic). A mixed type of influence is considered when the physiological system caused the dynamics of the initial moral influence, or vice versa, when the change of psychological characteristics leads to the emergence of a physiological shift.

"In extreme situations, the exposure of the human body can be of two types: uniformity of exposure and anxiety exposure. To know whether exposure belongs to one or another type is its characteristic, which is determined by the direction of exposure.

The main content of the answer in the same form is the specific influence of the organism, which is aimed at eliminating or overcoming the extreme factors and solving the moral issues. Then, at the moral level, the characteristic of the response is

a sufficiently conscious goal-directed character. This ensures the formation of a clear plan of human action based on a qualitative analysis of the entire existing situation, and sometimes on quantitative descriptions of extreme conditions.

The response pattern associated with anxiety sensitivity is characterized by the specific relationship of the extreme factor. It is primarily aimed at maintaining the functioning of the organism and maintaining the structure of the ongoing activity. In situations where conscious control of moral influence is weakened, unconscious moral acts are observed, such as panic. If in the same form of the response, the activity that existed before the beginning of the influence of the extreme factor remains unchanged, then in the second situation there is a decrease in the subjective necessity of these reasons, and a change in the type of reasoning. Anxiety sensitivity, as a rule, appears in strong extreme situations (perceived subjectively and objectively).

The same form of influence. A distinctive feature of the response form is its goal-oriented character, with the formation of an action plan aimed at eliminating or minimizing the effects of extreme conditions. The higher the concentration of attention, the greater the decrease in sensitivity. Then the increased concentration of attention in the movement of extreme factors is to ignore the extraneous signal that does not belong to the activity relationship. Specific changes are characteristic for memory processes, at the same time for working memory. For humans, semantic spirituality is enhanced only by remembering that material. This fact even stands out as one of the characteristic features of the response. It is characterized by an increase in the productivity of thinking - it is possible to talk about the speed of search and the flexibility of thinking.

At the moral level, changes are observed in the structure of activity. Stereotyped, tightly regulated sensitivity is complemented by actions based on consideration of the probability of a change in the situation, which leads to a variation of the activity algorithm. Then the number of errors can be increased, some of them will be conscious. The same effect is also observed with the growth of the role of qualities related to the individual's will, with the strengthening of the excitatory component involved in the formation of the response. The role of socially meaningful and highly civic causes will increase. But new reasons, as a rule, do not appear like this.

Panic sensitivity and its types.

The panic effect condition has little to do with its own characteristics and is of the same type that is relevant for a wide variety of situations. The degree of expressiveness of its qualitative content can vary several times: individual

components can be presented differently or not at all. However, the general structure of the response is constant.

Three main forms of response can be distinguished in the conditions of panic sensitivity: small, medium and final level. The low-level psychological state panic has much in common with the well-studied affectivity. It consists in analyzing the external influencer and evaluating its meaning. However, it differs from directed exposure in that the panic effect is more durable under the influence of a weak extreme factor, and the psychological moral components are more strongly expressed in it. More is a change in the scope of perception. At the moral level, the performance of professional skills is impaired. This is more clearly expressed in the slowing down of work. In general, the appearance of exposure to a small level of panic does not cause significant emotions. At the same time, the general direction of the movement and the ratio of the reasons for the activity do not change.

In the growth of an extreme situation, a moderate level of panic sensitivity develops. A characteristic feature of this exposure is the biasing of observed changes. If in the previous situation the scene of change could be sufficiently diverse, then now the expression of emotionality of various functions is observed. The emotional system increases to a certain extent. Memory skills are observed, attention span and performance of location problems are impaired. Impairment of attention and memory leads to increased activity errors. Their speed increases, the conscious control over the occurrence and correction of errors is disturbed, which leads to the appearance of a "chain" of errors - the first errors appear one after another in a stereotyped activity. This is conditioned by a decrease in control over the quality of activity, and a person diligently repeats the same erroneous action despite its inaccuracy. The structure of both fertility and reproductive intelligence operations changes. At the moral level, one of the essential signs is the change of reasons for activity. In the first place, the reasons for experiencing fear and getting out of an extreme situation are put forward. In dominant (main) conditions, it is the first of many causes that determine human activity. A vividly expressed exciting tension emerges.

The last level of exposure in panic can be in two forms: passive and active. However, both situations represent a loss of conscious control over behavior. In a sluggish form, a specific lump causes hardening, the cessation of active activity. Individual actions may continue, but they lose the character of a conscious goal. They are almost unable to receive the signals related to the feelings that arise. A person often does not understand the appeal to him. There will be no resistance to the active action of the extreme situation, it will be difficult to even talk about the character of

trying to leave it. An analysis focused on the past usually reveals complete or partial amnesia. Small details are taken into account in the memory, and important details are lost from the mind. Ambivalence syndrome also causes the emotional color of personal experience to be removed. Thus, when interviewing people who have experienced a natural disaster, they often describe their experiences like this: It's like it's me and it's not me, it's someone else: it's either poor affect control or It is characterized by In this situation, perception is preserved, even an algorithm of correct actions can be found, but the will does not allow them to be carried out.

At the moral level, the reason for leaving the situation is characteristic for the active form of the panic effect. He can also perform in a specific form (escape, run, leave) and accept the form of activity necessary in specific situations, but the organization of this activity is characterized by the absence of behavioral logic. Rather, it is a collection of separate, unrelated actions. They do not complete the elements of the movement, simple repetitions of the movement or alternation of one movement are opposite to directed ones. It is necessary to determine the beliefs of persons in this situation. However, the possibility of a homogenous group perception may not lead to the desired result, but may invite new types of conflicting actions that have not been encountered before.

In the active form of the panic effect, the double consciousness syndrome described above does not occur. Along with persuasion, this threat leads to exposure. Their final form is panic. For example, for this form of affectivity, the dominant idea is characteristic, and the behavior is manifested by a more active personality.

Extreme state dynamics. Panic effect, (especially its last forms); as a rule, under exactly the same conditions, it is observed with an increase in stress, mental strain, and emotional tension. Thus, the extremity of the situation leads to the development of a negative mental state, the dynamics of which have the following form: uniform form of response - panic effect - mental or emotional tension - stress - distress.

Psychic tension can appear in human activity when there are specific factors that present increased demands on human knowledge, capabilities, and resources, or when there is an obstacle to the goals set before them. Mental tension is usually known as anger, fatigue, excitement, and negative experiences. In the physiological state, hyperfunction of some processes is observed, such as rapid pulse, increased pressure, sweating. At the same time, exposure time may decrease, time indicators may increase, and the number of errors and false alarms may increase.

The deepening of these factors leads to the emergence of stress, the reasons for which are hidden in the incompatibility of opportunities based on the nature of the human

condition and working conditions. However, not all stress is destructive. If the stressful situation is considered to be a positive force, it is called eustress, weakened, excessive stress is called distress, and different types of stress, such as exciting and informational, are distinguished in professional activity. Then its various forms (impulsive, inhibitory, generalized) lead to changes in mental processes, excitatory shifts, the causal structure of activity, movement and behavior disorders.

Large individual differences are observed in reactions to a stressful situation. Some people are adapted to stress, others not so much. However, in any situation, constant pressure does not affect health. If the positive and negative stresses often replace each other, the pressure increases continuously; and as a result of a sharp decrease in the immune system, health is damaged. That's why it is necessary to carefully check the stress tolerance when selecting individuals for a specialty associated with stressful situations.

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